

**METHOD FOR EVALUATION OF ELASTIC
PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES
WITH VARIOUS LEVELS OF POROSITY**

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ABSTRACT

A new analytical approach to determine elastic properties of continuous carbon fiber reinforced composite laminates with various levels of porosity is proposed. The model is based on a thermo-mechanical constitutive theory for elastic composites with distributed damage, originally proposed by Allen, et. al (1987). The model utilizes second-order tensor valued internal state variables to represent porosity and the relationship between ultrasonic NDT (Non-Destructive Testing) output and physical porosity distribution through the laminate thickness which was established by extensive photomicrographic examination for different porosity levels for both tape and cloth laminates. The equations for the engineering constants were developed.

Keywords: composites, porosity, elastic properties, non-destructive testing.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most common anomalies which can be present in cured carbon fiber reinforced composite laminates used for military and civil aircraft structures is porosity. Porosity is usually defined as a concentration of the microscopic interfacial voids which are caused by entrapped air or solvent volatiles during the curing process. Several factors can contribute to the void formation: chemical composition, resin mixing and prepregging procedures, tooling, laminate thickness and geometry, amount of bleeder used (for full resin systems), type and geometry of pressure intensifier, moisture content, etc. The typical examples of stiffness and strength reduction for porous composite laminates are given in Reference [1].

Analytical techniques to determine porous laminate stiffness and residual strength are not currently available. Therefore a variety of expensive and time-consuming structural tests are performed to verify the effects of porosity levels in different laminate thicknesses and stacking sequences for each composite material and mode of failure (notched room temperature and elevated temperature/moisturized compression, interlaminar shear, bearing, etc.). Furthermore, the change in laminate stiffness due to excessive porosity can alter structure load path and buckling design criteria. It is important for the designer to be able to predict the porous laminate properties.

A new methodology is proposed in which elastic constants for composite laminates with different porosity levels can be determined based on non-porous laminate properties and the quantitative output of ultrasonic NDT techniques. In order to achieve this task, the NDT sound attenuation data is correlated to the actual porosity/voids distribution through the thickness of the laminate by examining numerous photomicrographs for both tape and cloth laminates. The thermo-mechanical constitutive theory for elastic composites with distributed damage, originally proposed by Allen [2], is utilized to develop an analytical model for porous laminate properties where porosity is represented by second-order tensor valued internal state variables. The NDT output representing different levels of porosity is reflected in developed equations for elastic constants.

2. ULTRASONIC NDT OF POROUS LAMINATES

The most common ultrasonic NDT techniques used in aircraft industry for evaluation of large composite components are through-transmission and pulse-echo. For both techniques, the sound attenuation is determined from the amplitude of the wave after traveling through the test part. This commonly used test utilizes a longitudinal ultrasonic beam which is incident normal to composite surface. The difference between these two NDT techniques is the way in which the sound is transmitted and received. For the through-transmission technique, two piezo-electric transducers are used on each side of the laminate as transmitter and receiver. For the pulse-echo technique a single transducer is used for transmitting and receiving the sound as it travels through the laminate thickness and reflects back at the opposite surface of the laminate. The common ultrasonic inspection frequencies range between 2.25 and 10 MHz. The sound attenuation levels in the laminate are measured in decibels (dB).

In the aircraft industry a squirter through-transmission system is typically used for the large parts (wing skins, fuselage components, etc.). The schematic of one such system, AUSS V (McDonnell Douglas Corporation), is shown in Figure 1. The attenuation in composites is relatively high, primarily due to scattering by the fibers and isothermal absorption in the resin. If porosity is present, the scattering is significantly increased.

The components contributing to the total sound loss during porous laminate non-destructive inspection are described in Figure 1. To obtain the sound attenuation due to porosity, the non-porous reference standard attenuation is compared to the part attenuation:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta A &= (A_1 + A_2 + A_3 + A_4 + A_5)_{\text{porous laminate}} - (A_1 + A_2 + A_3 + A_4)_{\text{ref. standard}} \\ &= A_5 + 2\alpha_{\text{por.}} t_{\text{por.}} - 2\alpha_{\text{ref.}} t_{\text{ref.}} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Assuming $2\alpha_{\text{por.}} t_{\text{por.}} \approx 2\alpha_{\text{ref.}} t_{\text{ref.}}$, the actual sound loss due to the presence of porosity, A_5 , can be determined. The high ΔdB value represents higher levels of porosity in the laminate.

Today in the aerospace industry the most common technique to evaluate the elastic properties and strength reduction for composite laminates with various levels of porosity is to perform numerous mechanical tests. The ΔdB attenuation is correlated to the elastic constants/strength of laminates. These tests are performed for each product form (fiber and resin combinations), various failure modes (notched compression, interlaminar shear, bearing, etc.) and for various porosity levels (0 to 60 ΔdB attenuation). Typical examples of the plots generated using such data can be found in References [3,4].

$$A_T \quad (\text{Total Sound Loss}) = 20 \log \frac{V_1}{V_2} = A_1 + A_2 + A_3 + A_4 + A_5$$

$$A_1 \quad (\text{Losses at the Front Water/Laminate Interface Surface}) = 10 \log \frac{(Z_{\text{comp}} - Z_{\text{water}})^2}{(Z_{\text{comp}} + Z_{\text{water}})^2}$$

Z - Acoustic Impedance

$$A_2 \quad (\text{Losses at the Back Laminate/Water Interface Surface}) = A_1$$

$$A_3 \quad (\text{Attenuation in Composite Laminate}) = 2\alpha t$$

α - Linear Attenuation Coefficient of the Medium (Approximate 20 dB/in. at 5 MHz for Carbon/Epoxy)

t - Laminate Thickness

$$A_4 = \text{Combination of the Transmitter/Receiver Electromechanical Response, Transmitter and Receiver Defraction, Phase Cancellation Effects, Backscatter at Interfaces, Surface Roughness, AUSS System Calibration Errors, etc}$$

$$A_5 = \text{Wave Scattering/Sound Loss Due to Porosity}$$

Figure 1. Components of Total Sound Loss Equation
 Ultrasonic Through-Transmission Squirter NDT Technique

3. NEW METHODOLOGY FOR EVALUATION OF POROUS LAMINATES

Because the mechanical tests that are currently performed to evaluate the strength and stiffness are very expensive and time-consuming, an analytical technique for evaluation of elastic constants for porous composites laminates is needed. The properties determined using the analytical technique would still require verification, but with a significantly lower number of test specimens.

The technique proposed in this paper consists of using the quantitative input from ultrasonic through-transmission NDT data, establishing the relationship between these data and the actual size and location of voids/interlaminar delaminations, and finally utilizing this information in an analytical model. A flowchart showing an outline of porous laminate stiffness evaluation is shown in Figure 2.

The distribution of porosity through the thickness of the laminate and individual pore size was determined for AS4/3501-6 and T300/3501-6 unidirectional and eight harness woven carbon/epoxy by evaluating numerous photomicrographs of laminates with different levels of porosity. Typical void distribution through the thickness for these laminates is shown in Figure 3. Although the void distribution is different for cloth and tape laminates, as expected more voids were trapped in the middle of the laminates. During cure there was no significant

Figure 2. Flowchart Showing Development of Stiffness Evaluation Technique for Woven and Unidirectional Laminates With Various Degrees of Porosity

void distribution for laminates with thickness ranging from 1.0 to 8.0 mm. The void (or interlaminar delamination) distribution for more recently developed toughened epoxy material is currently being evaluated, but the shape of the curve is not expected to change significantly.

The voids for the woven laminates could approximately be represented as circular interply cracks about 0.5 mm in diameter. For the tape laminates the voids are cigar-shaped interply cracks running along the fiber direction with length between 0.25 to 2.50 mm. The size of the voids was consistent for the laminates between 1.0 to 8.0 mm thick.

Figure 3. Porosity Distribution in Carbon/Epoxy Laminates

The difference between ultrasonic attenuation (dB) for porous laminates and the non-porous reference standard is obtained using a method similar to a current NDT approach. These data are correlated to the total interply delamination length (all analysis performed per unit width) and subsequently to the void distribution through the thickness based on the previously developed relationship (Figure 4).

The analytical model to determine the elastic properties of the laminate with porosity is based on Allen's, et. al [2,5] theory which proposes to model damage in composite laminates using second-order tensor valued internal state variables. The internal state variables are defined from a locally volume averaged displacement vector, u_i , and its corresponding unit outer normal, n_j :

$$\alpha_{ij} = \frac{1}{V_L} \int_S u_i n_j dS \quad (2)$$

where V_L is a local volume and S is the void surface area. The internal state variables describe the kinematics of the locally averaged measures of the interply void cracking process within the local volume (V_L) and are strain-like quantities.

The model takes the form of laminate microanalysis equations with porosity represented as an internal state variable. The internal state variables are related to the strain energy release rate for interply delaminations using an approach similar to O'Brien's [6] as shown in Figure 5.

The equations for evaluation of the elastic constants for porous laminates in the case of symmetrical, balanced laminates with interply voids located approximately symmetric with respect to the laminate midplane were developed:

Figure 4. Correlation Between Through Transmission NDT and Porosity (Void Length)

$$E_x = \frac{1}{t} \left(\sum_{K=1}^n [Q_{11}]_K - \sum_{j=1}^3 \left(\sum_{K=1}^n [Q_{11}]_K - \frac{1}{t} \sum_{m=1}^{n+1} [Q_{11}]_m t_m \right) \frac{2l_j}{w} \right)$$

$$E_y = \frac{1}{t} \left(\sum_{K=1}^n [Q_{22}]_K - \sum_{j=1}^3 \left(\sum_{K=1}^n [Q_{22}]_K - \frac{1}{t} \sum_{m=1}^{n+1} [Q_{22}]_m t_m \right) \frac{2l_j}{w} \right)$$

(3)

$$V_{xy} = \frac{\sum_{K=1}^n [Q_{12}]_K - \sum_{j=1}^3 \left(\sum_{K=1}^n [Q_{12}]_K - \frac{1}{t} \sum_{m=1}^{n+1} [Q_{12}]_m t_m \right) \frac{2l_j}{w}}{\sum_{K=1}^n [Q_{22}]_K - \sum_{j=1}^3 \left(\sum_{K=1}^n [Q_{22}]_K - \frac{1}{t} \sum_{m=1}^{n+1} [Q_{22}]_m t_m \right) \frac{2l_j}{w}}$$

$$G = \frac{1}{t} \left(\sum_{K=1}^n [Q_{66}]_K - \sum_{j=1}^3 \left(\sum_{K=1}^n [Q_{66}]_K - \frac{1}{t} \sum_{m=1}^{n+1} [Q_{66}]_m t_m \right) \frac{2l_j}{w} \right)$$

Subscripts: k = number of plies

j = three sections of interest (see Figure 5 for woven laminates)

m = number of delaminated sublaminates

l_j = length of porous section

w = total length, representing 4.8 mm (3/16 inch) squirter diameter

[Q_{pq}] = undamaged laminate or sublaminates stiffness components

Figure 5. Rule of Mixture Analysis for Interply Voids

The detailed derivation of Equation 3 and the correlation of analytical and experimental results correlation are presented by Rubin and Jerina [7]. The actual measured compression and shear modulus values for AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy specimens with different levels of porosity showed generally good correlation to analytically predicted values.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposes a methodology for evaluation of elastic properties of laminates with various degrees of porosity. A correlation between quantitative ultrasonic non-destructive testing output and physical distribution of interply voids/delaminations was established. The analytical model based on Allen's thermo-mechanical constitutive theory for elastic composites with anomalies (porosity) and utilizing non-destructive evaluation techniques for assessment of porosity level was developed.

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